

DESIGN, FABRICATION AND PRELIMINARY SIMULATION OF A MULTISTABLE KIRIGAMI STRUCTURE

A. Lele, A. Balasubrahmanian, S. Li¹, and O. Myers^{1*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Clemson University, Clemson, SC USA, * Corresponding author (omyers@clemson.edu)

Keywords: *Kirigami, Bi-stable, Composites*

ABSTRACT

Composite materials have developed with the development of different applications. It has led to the development of some of the most state-of-the-art smart materials and active structures. One example of such an active material would be a rotor wing of a helicopter made of pre-stressed bistable composite laminates. Researchers have taken inspiration from such active structures to create complex shape-generating patterns using the art of Kirigami. They have studied a unit cell which combines two bistable carbon fiber patches arranged in a Kirigami pattern. This pattern helps to generate a complex 3-D mechanical system from a 2-D structure. This resultant structure can possess variable stiffness under different states of shape and loading. This paper begins to analyze the feasibility of expanding a simple Kirigami unit cell to a structure involving multiple Kirigami unit cells. It also tries to answer questions about the fabrication of such a complex structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the early '80s, Hyer discovered the bi-stable behavior of unsymmetric fiber reinforced laminates and studied these "Bi-stable" composites in-depth[1]–[3]. Many applications were suggested to put the bi-stable laminates to use, however, these laminates were not the strongest structures to be used in an engineering application. Recently, due to the development of advanced smart materials and active structures, the bi-stable laminates were revisited as a potential fundamental unit of a larger multistable structure. Two bi-stable patches were combined into a zig-zag Kirigami pattern and a Kirigami unit cell was fabricated.[4] This Kirigami unit cell was multi-stable and exhibited 4 stable states of configuration. The two patches of the Kirigami unit cell had an opposable orthogonal [0/90] and a [90/0] layup respectively, which led to the generation of the 4 multistable states. The Kirigami unit cell is considered as the most fundamental unit of a larger multistable Kirigami inspired structure. This gives the Kirigami multistable structure a simpler post-curing shape. However, when each patch of the Kirigami multistable structure is snapped, a very complex and an almost-helical shape is observed. This is observed in the presence of an alternate [0/90] and [90/0] layup on the neighboring patches. If the patch layup is varied slightly by arranging two neighboring patches to have the same [0/90] layup followed by the next two patches with a [90/0] layup, a completely different post-curing, and post-snap shape will be observed. These results were compared with simulation studies to validate the FEA. Furthermore, the Kirigami unit cell was tested and it was observed that it exhibited different stiffness behaviors in different configurations or shapes. This theory can be extended to the Kirigami multistable structure and one can predict that it will also exhibit a variable stiffness behavior. This can be particularly useful in applications that require a tailored stiffness response situation. Thus, stiffness programming can be introduced in the Kirigami multistable structure to adhere it to the demands of different scenarios.

Figure 1.2 represents prototypes fabricated with multiple Kirigami unit cells as well as the simulated models. The multistable Kirigami composite model illustrated in Figure 1.2 (c) and (d) is essentially the same structure with an altered layup. Thus, we refer to these models as "Isotopes". The work involves the development of experimental procedures to study the multistable Kirigami laminates. It will also involve the determination of the snap-through and snapback characteristics for the multistable models

in addition to the stiffness characteristics. Additionally, it will involve extending the simulation procedure discussed in this thesis to the multistable model. Moreover, it will also be interesting to compare isotopes in terms of their multistable behavior and snap-through characteristics. These recommendations will be the appropriate way forward in achieving the ultimate research objectives of the Kirigami composites project. The unit cell and thereafter, the Multi-stable laminate are modeled in ABAQUS® CAE for behavioral study and deeper understanding.

Figure 1.1: Kirigami Unit Cell as defined for further use into a Multistable structure [5]

Figure 1.2: Kirigami Multistable Laminates (a) and (b) represent the fabricated structure. (c) and (d) represent the Kirigami multistable simulated results as isotopes

The concept of Kirigami or jianzhi, monkiri or silhouette has been derived from the ancient art of Origami which explores the creation of structures by the folding of virtually unstretchable surfaces. To further advance the concept of Origami for the creation of structures using metamaterials and adaptive structures, Kirigami allows the creation of complex three-dimensional structures from thin 2D sheets of material. Instead of limiting to folding, Kirigami opens another dimension of creativity by a combination folding with cutting. An art that was initially limited to “pop-up” books has now found its application in the field of engineering, one such being the development of honeycomb material fabricated using the

simultaneous use of the folding and cutting principles of Kirigami, thereby achieving shape morphing capabilities. [6] In this case, the Multi-stable Kirigami laminates have the ability to snap their structure or alter its physical form into a different stable state by undergoing a necessary transition.

Figure 1.3: Kirigami Zigzag pattern sample [7]

2 FABRICATION

Figure 2.1: Lay-up pattern of the Kirigami Unit cell with the orthogonal orientation of composite fibers [5]

The samples were fabricated using DA 409U/G35-150 prepreg fiber sheets which are a Unidirectional Carbon Fiber pre-impregnated and partially cured with an Epoxy resin system which is required to be cured under heat and vacuum at 121 °C/270 °F and 30 psi simultaneously for 1 hour. The prepreps are carefully stored in a freezing environment below 4 °C/40 °F as per manufacturer requirements and subsequently cut to the Kirigami patterns using a pair of scissors or paper knives. The use of prepreps, while they are still at freezing temperatures, is critical to the process as it ensures that the volatile solvents present in the epoxy may not evaporate before the curing process is initiated.

The base ply of the Kirigami laminate unit cell has a dimension of 133 mm (5.25 inches) X 127 mm (5 inches) as indicated in Figure 2.1 with a slit 101.6 mm (4 inches) long and 6.35 mm (0.25 inches) cut into it. The laminates are constructed by using the fiber sheets oriented in the desired manner in

alternative 0° or 90° laminates. The arranged laminates are subsequently cured under vacuum pressure with a complete vacuum-bagging setup and then put through its elevated temperature cure cycle. A 0.6m X 0.6m X 4mm aluminum plate is used as the mold for the bagging setup which is first prepped by cleaning with acetone and then a mold release agent is applied to it. Then the uncured laminate is laid down on the plate, followed by a layer of high-temperature perforated release film (10 LYD 3015-PERF-D- Release Ply- High Temp 450F- Perforated Film), subsequently, the peel ply (10 LYD 3000-D-Econo Ply J Polyester Peel Ply) is placed and then the absorbent breather fabric (10 LYD 3011-D-Breather Fabric). A two-part vacuum connector is then placed in the vicinity and the seal is made using tacky tape and vacuum bagging film (10 LYD 3014-D - Stretchlon SL200 Vacuum Bag Film). The nozzle of the vacuum connector is connected to a vacuum pump (1 EA. VacuMaster 5 CFM Vacuum Pump) and the vacuum seal is checked before it is placed into the preheated oven at $121^\circ\text{C}/270^\circ\text{F}$ where it is left for elevated temperature curing for 1 hour. After completion of 1 hour, the samples are removed and let to cool to room temperature at which the cooling induces thermal stresses in the laminates which then causes the bistability. Post-cure the samples are extracted after cutting open the vacuum bag and other materials used in the process at which point the laminate is observed to have settled into one of the stable equilibrium states as indicated in Figure 1.2. Mechanical force or displacement is used to cause the laminate to snap into its other stable states. The Kirigami unit cell has four different stable states denoted using the binary code [00], [01], [10], [11] as indicated in Figure 2.2.

Care must be taken in the precise alignment of the 0° and 90° fibers to ensure that the results are accurate and consistent throughout. Formation of air bubbles between the plies must also be prevented by careful lay-up and rolling of the samples before curing.

Figure 2.2: Binary notation for the multiple stable states of a Kirigami Unit cell [5]

3 SIMULATIONS

The model being simple to create, is designed with alternate [0/90] configuration in ABAQUS® CAE software to simulate the curing and snapping of individual unit cells to understand the critical displacement and forces required to cause the actual snapping. Individual legs of the unit cell are snapped while the tabs connecting them are held clamped by a ZERO displacement condition under the Boundary Conditions in ABAQUS®. The snapping is simulated by application of a ramped displacement similar to a Displacement Control testing setup. The history output feature in ABAQUS® is used to determine the required quantities while the tab is kept fixed. For the purpose of assuring that the achieved state is, in fact, a stable state, a free step is added post snapping with only the fixed boundary condition on the tabs where it is made sure that the laminate retains its shape as observed post-snap throughout the time period of this step. This modeling setup is based on practical testing performed on the Kirigami unit-cell as part of initial research for this work. The alternate [0/90] laminate setup is

observed to an almost helical shape after snapping of each of the three linked Kirigami unit cells. ABAQUS® requires various material properties like modulus of Elasticity and Rigidity (E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , G_{13} , G_{23}), coefficient of thermal expansion (α_1 , α_2), Poisson’s ratio (ν_{12}) and the values used for DA 409U/G35-150 was used as found in literature [8], [9] and is listed in Table 1.

Property for DA 409R/G35-150	Value
Tensile Modulus	18.8 Msi (129 Gpa)
Flexural Modulus	17.9 Msi (123.4 Gpa)
E_1	135 Gpa
E_2	9.5 Gpa
G_{12}	5 Gpa
G_{13}	7.17 Gpa
G_{23}	3.97 Gpa
ν_{12}	0.3
α_1	$-2 \times 10^{-8}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
α_2	$-3.27 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
t (Ply thickness)	0.15 mm

Table 1: Material properties used for simulations [9]

Figure 3.1: Meshing of the Multistable Kirigami Laminate with 1.5 Global size on ABAQUS CAE

Once the geometry is designed, the “Composite Section” tab in ABAQUS® is used to assign the corresponding layup for the laminate wherein, the appropriate orientation of the fibers with respect to the X-axis and thickness of each ply is provided as an input and the appropriate material properties are assigned once the layup sequences are defined as in Figure 2.1. Thick shell S4R elements are used to mesh the Kirigami Multistable Laminate, since they are suitable for relatively low shear moduli, resulting in the shear deformation of the composites being included similar to a thick shell. 2mm quadrilateral elements are used to mesh the laminates as found to be required from previous work. [5] The meshed laminate in ABAQUS® is showed in Figure 3.1. The first step of the study involves the simulation of the curing cycle of the process. A ramped cooling process is applied from 121°C (250°F)

to 20°C (68°F) while it is completely clamped or fixed and released subsequently at the end of the cycle, creating conditions similar to the fabrication process where the laminate is cured and then cooled down under vacuum pressure which is later released. Notably, it is required that the NLGEOM option is always on “ON” throughout the whole process so that the system will perform a non-linear analysis. Based upon the post-cure shape, suitable boundary conditions are applied in the form of a displacement control setup to cause snapping of the laminate into the various stable states as indicated in Figure 3.4. The tab geometry is fixed to simulate a clamped tab in a practical setup in order to study the snap-through behavior, thereby defining one necessary boundary condition. A displacement is applied to a point on the laminate, in an appropriate direction as evident from the post-cure shape of the laminate to cause the snapping, followed by a stabilization step where only the fixed boundary condition is applied and the displacement is deactivated, thereby revealing the stable snapped shape of the laminate.

Figure 3.2: Fixed tab boundary conditions applied on a representative unit cell of the multistable laminate [5]

Node Number	Reaction Force (N)	Critical displacement (mm)
1	1.4	41.8
2	0.7	31.2
3	0.3	31.2
4	0.3	39.2
5	0.29	39.01
6	1.01	35.8

Table 2: Reaction forces and critical displacements at the nodes

Figure 3.3 Post snap shapes of both isotopes of the multistable configuration

Figure 3.4 (a) Post-cure shape (b) First snap of the laminate (b) Second leg of the first unit cell snapped (c) Snapping the second unit cell (d) Second leg of the second unit cell snapped (e) Both legs of the third unit cell snapped at the same time using opposing displacements

4 CONCLUSION

Based on existing literature and work upon the Kirigami Unit cell, a standard simulation procedure is developed and put to use to study the curing and snap-through behavior of the Kirigami multistable laminate. This study was also used to determine the reaction forces and critical displacements at the nodes where the snapping is caused in the form of ramped displacement. The combination of the art of Kirigami and Bistability in composites are used to fabricate and analyze a complex structure with a multitude of stable states wherein a simplified structured termed as Kirigami unit cell is built upon to produce the Kirigami Multistable system using the DA 409U/G35-150 carbon fiber prepregs fabrics. The process of fabrication involved cutting of the fibers to form individual plies of the laminate required

to form the Kirigami patten, followed by pressurized, elevated temperature curing in an oven. The interesting aspect of Kirigami laminates observed is that despite being connected by a tab, they are capable of displaying independent behavior in the snap-through process and are reversible by application of a snap-back step.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] M.-L. Dano and M. W. Hyer, "Snap-through of unsymmetric fiber-reinforced composite laminates."
- [2] M.-L. Dano and M. W. Hyer, "THERMALLY-INDUCED DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF UNSYMMETRIC LAMINATES," 1998.
- [3] M. W. Hyer, "Calculations of the Room-Temperature Shapes of Unsymmetric Laminates," *Compos. Mater.*, vol. 15, no. July, pp. 296–310, 1981.
- [4] A. Lele, O. J. Myers, and S. Li, "SMASIS 2018_Aditya Lelelatest_SL_April 23." ASME, 2018.
- [5] A. G. Lele, "TigerPrints An Investigative Study of the Snapthrough, Snapback and the Stiffness Properties of a Kirigami Unit Cell," 2018.
- [6] R. M. Neville, F. Scarpa, and A. Pirrera, "Shape morphing Kirigami mechanical metamaterials," *Sci. Rep.*, 2016.
- [7] Z. Song *et al.*, "Kirigami-based stretchable lithium-ion batteries," *Sci. Rep.*, 2015.
- [8] S. Annamalai, "Design of Bistable Composite Laminates for Shape Morphing Applications," 2016.
- [9] P. Portela, P. Camanho, P. Weaver, and I. Bond, "Analysis of morphing, multi stable structures actuated by piezoelectric patches," *Comput. Struct.*, vol. 86, no. 3–5, pp. 347–356, 2008.